

Translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial programme at a South African university

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This qualitative study explores translanguaging pedagogical practices in the undergraduate tutorial classroom at a South African university. The paper reports that tutors and tutees draw from their different linguistic repertoires to make sense of the facilitation of learning in the tutorials. In this process, they decide which languages to use and when and how to deploy them to enhance their tutorial practices. To generate data, tutors and tutees participated in semi-structured and focus group discussions. Translanguaging theory was utilised as a theoretical framework. Data were then analysed using thematic analysis. Findings showed that translanguaging pedagogical practices have the potential to (a) assist tutors and tutees in creating a comfortable space for learning and (b) enhance content understanding and collaborative learning, and (c) could be valuable in decolonising tutorial pedagogies. Tutors indicated that they require specialised tutor training on how to use translanguaging in multilingual tutorials.

Keywords: Multilingualism; South African Universities; Translanguaging; Tutees; Tutorials; Tutors

1. Introduction

The demise of the apartheid in South Africa brought hope for the previously marginalised, particularly those who suffered from systemic exclusion, be it political, socio-economic or educational participation. With regard to the higher education sector and deep into the third decade of the democratic dispensation, sluggish progress has been witnessed in developing and promoting indigenous languages. Khumalo and Nkomo (2022) take this further, arguing that in addition to a lack of development, there is also a challenge of parity of esteem as elucidated in the constitution. This is despite the constitutional and legislative provisions that engender the need to advance these languages (DHET 2015; DHET 2018). This recourse is an imperative social justice and decolonial issue, particularly in South Africa, wherein there is a need for redressing colonial and apartheid linguistic and epistemic access challenges faced by students in multilingual tutorial classrooms. Not much has been written about the intersection between tutoring and multilingualism in South

African universities. The following section discusses tutoring in teaching and learning.

Tutorials as informal teaching and learning spaces have been reported to be impactful against the plight of student academic success at universities (Layton, 2015; Kahu & Picton, 2019). Albeit the demonstrated benefit of tutorials, they remain on the cusp of alienating students from their linguistic repertoires for the purpose of teaching and learning as they often veer onto the sliding slope of monolingual biases and advance a view of thinking about languages as sealed entities (Makalela, 2015). Therefore, many universities in South Africa with a similar tutorial system view multilingualism as a natural phenomenon (Du Buisson, 2017).

In this regard, I argue that translanguaging pedagogical practices have the potential, or ‘affordance’ à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), to redress linguistic and epistemic access injustices incurred by students at a South African institution. Scholars of translanguaging¹ have ably shown that translanguaging which includes “the multiple discursive practices in which bilinguals engage in order to make sense of their bilingual worlds” (García & Li, 2014, p. 65), presents opportunities for multilingual students to make ‘meaning’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2022) of their worldviews through the flexible use of the linguistic varieties in the classroom (Makalela, 2016). Kiramba (2016) posits that translanguaging could effectively address the challenges of teaching multilingual classrooms in educational settings. Baker (2001, p. 281) posits that there are four major educational benefits to translanguaging: (1) it may promote a deeper and fuller understanding of the subject matter, (2) it may help the development of the weaker language, (3) it may facilitate home-school links and cooperation, and (4) it may help the integration of fluent speakers with early learners.

In this paper, I argue that in as much as translanguaging as a pedagogical practice is fraught with possibilities of learning content using input and output strategy, it is noteworthy to recognise that there is a gap in the application of translanguaging as a pedagogical practice in South African higher education. Against this background, I ask:

- How does translanguaging as a pedagogical practice aid in facilitating multilingual tutorials at a South African university?

2. Background

The intersection of the two concepts of tutoring and translanguaging has not gained prominence in higher education in recent years, even though literature is scarce on the existence of both in a multilingual tutorial classroom (Falchikov, 2001; Makalela, 2015, 2016; Mazak & Carroll, 2016; Saunders,

1992). Tutoring comprises role-taking and knowledge difference, where a student plays the role of being a tutor and another a tutee. Of importance to note is that tutors are not subject experts. Hence, their role is limited to the facilitation of tutorials. For example, Reznicek-Parrado's (2020) study on translanguaging in peer tutorials shows that tutors and students used translanguaging to achieve two goals: (1) enhancing academic literacy, and (2) building community. On academic support, findings show that over and beyond their contribution to writing skills (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016, 2018b, 2023b) for a specific course, tutors immensely contributed to the 'academic literacy trajectories' of tutees as imperative to students' academic success. With respect to community building, Reznicek-Parrado (2020) found that "tutors are consistently invested in their student's academic (and personal) well-being, thus positioning the teaching and learning environment of the tutoring room as an opportunity to build a community" (Reznicek-Parrado 2020, pp. 7-11).

Given this background, this paper focuses on translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial system, which is perceived as a mechanism for mitigating throughput success rate and epistemic access. It is necessary to note that myriad factors need to be considered when providing tutoring support to multilingual students. For example, Thonus (2014) argues that support for multilingual students is necessary; Thonus further proposes that we either train our tutors in a one-size-fits-all strategy, or train tutors in specific methods to tutor monolingual and multilingual students. This approach might be helpful, particularly in the South African context. Tutor training is imperative for ensuring that pedagogical practices and facilitation of teaching and learning in multilingual tutorials are maintained.

Reporting on a multilingual tutorials study at Cape Peninsula University, Leach (2015) indicated that many students posited that their home language helped them engage in the discussions during tutorials. This indicates that tutorials are safe spaces that can be used to promote diverse languages brought by students. Mwaniki (2016) found that it is normal for students when they need clarity on a particular concept; they will sit in groups to discuss using L1 and later revert to a tutorial/lecture where they share their understanding of the concepts in English. He concluded that this type of learning was encouraged because evidence shows it to be an effective method in "clarifying linguistics concepts being taught/learnt" (Mwaniki, 2016, p. 206; cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016). Hungwe (2019) conducted a study in a multilingual undergraduate class, or a 'petri dish' à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023a), in a South African university and posited that when students were given leverage to tap into their diverse linguistic and cultural repertoires, it helped them understand and make meaning of the subject matter—for more on 'meaning', see Salmani Nodoushan (2022).

Similarly, Nomlomo and Katiya (2018) also reported similar findings in the study conducted at the University of Western Cape; the study focused on the experiences of first-year students enrolled in engineering courses. Their findings demonstrate that students reported cognitive benefits of deepening their understanding of the course using multilingual glossaries that helped them increase their academic performance (Nomlomo & Katiya 2018). The preceding finding corroborates what Cele (2021) opines: African languages could be utilised to aid students in comprehending subject concepts. The latter argument is imperative for the success of facilitating multilingual tutorials and to achieve the goal of the tutorials—that is, to help students engage and collaborate with the content with their peers. More so, Madiba (2018) undertook a study to explore how translanguaging was used in the economic tutorials at a multilingual university. However, in his findings, students demonstrated the use of translanguaging during their tutorials, even though the study's aim was not to assess the use of translanguaging. Students were unaware of this pedagogical practice (Madiba 2018). By doing so, the student's learning was maximised during the tutorials dealing with the problematic concept that could demotivate students to interact during the tutorials.

Translanguaging scholars aver that it emancipates both learner and teacher. It further transforms power relations by positioning the learning and teaching process on creating meaning-making. Hurst and Mona (2017) have shown that translanguaging could be perceived as a social justice pedagogy (Chaka, 2024). This suggests positive feedback (cf. Rodriguez et al., 2021) from students as they find their languages valued and legitimised in the learning space. Hurst and Mona's (2017) findings on the tutorials show that English remains language of instruction and suggest that providing different language options for tutor groups by deploying multilingual tutors is vital for classroom pedagogy.

On the other hand, translanguaging has been considered to valorise student experience in bilingual or multilingual classrooms. In other studies, translanguaging was reported to have played a role in shaping the identity of both teachers and students (Cenoz & Gorter, 2020; Creese & Blackledge, 2015; García, 2009; García & Alvis, 2019; Maseko, 2022; Paudel, 2021). Makalela (2015) aptly demonstrated that the translanguaging strategy enforces a deeper understanding of the content. His findings show a reconfiguration of teacher identity in the sense that there was a shift from “monolingual teacher to multilingual teacher” (p. 212). He argued that this was sparked by creating multilingual spaces in class. Ndlhovu and Makalela's (2021) study that focused on multilingual tutorials found that translanguaging could be one of the strategies to decolonise multilingualism in African universities. Even though classroom practices and curricula remain on the cusp of monolingual bias, this necessitates the call to decolonise these monolingual classroom practices.

In an integrative review study, Chaka (2020) argues that translanguaging is “a disruptive decolonial practice” (p. 26) as it rejects the notion of colonial and Western-centric perception of languages as bounded, named, and separate units. This is grounded in the view that translanguaging practices counter the monolingual conception by noting language borders as “ideological edifices” (Chaka, 2020, p. 26) constructed through Europeans by marginalising minority languages. Chaka (2020) cautions against misunderstanding or misapplication of decolonial practice in that adding a language practice to existing normal language practice does not imply a decolonial practice unless it is well substantiated by an explicit decolonial act. This view augurs well with Jaspers's (2018) critique that translanguaging has limitations; even though its scholars embed words such as 'transformation' and 'newness', it appears to be recreating the monolingual convictions it criticises. Makoni (2012) points out that it is not clear what languaging means in trans-languaging and argues the frameworks contradict the idea of perceiving language as a social action. These are some of the limitations that need to be critically engaged to avert the effect of advocating for plural monolingualism. Jaspers (2018) further points out that evidence shows that translanguaging might lead to a “decrease in well-being” (p. 7) and that students might not find it as liberating as it is currently claimed. Critical perspective on translanguaging is imperative as it helps us locate and carve the current discourse in a more balanced yet radical way. It is essential that we do not fall prey to a colonial conceptualisation of language use in higher education.

Given the colonial language conception in higher education, Ndhlovu and Makalela (2021) have made a clarion call to decolonising African multilingualism. Ndhlovu and Makalela (2021) state that universities do not permit students to draw from their multilingual resources. Instead, universities use a unilingual approach that marginalises the students' “ways of meaning-making and identity expression” (p. 55). They further argue that it is possible to disrupt monolingual bias in universities if “classroom practices, curricula, and policies” are based on the “multiple repertoires of the students and acknowledge the linguistic fluidities” (Makalela, 2021, p. 55). The tensions on the use of English-only could be linked with the colonial arrangement. The impact of colonial arrangement in marginalising indigenous languages in teaching and learning captures the notion of “coloniality of language” (Veronelli, 2015). This notion introduces the concept of “monolanguaging,” which denotes “a way of living together that includes one-way communication that dehumanises the colonised interlocutor” (Veronelli, 2015, p. 124). This discursive practice is tacit in a university classroom, as students who are not proficient in the language of instruction are dehumanised in knowledge production. The question that begs a response is whether decolonising multilingualism will provide an avenue for reclaiming the dignity of the

dehumanised. The answer could be found in the meaning of decolonisation as it has received prominence in higher education.

In this paper, decolonisation implies the disruption of the normalised monolingual classroom practices in higher education. I use translanguaging as a theoretical framework to aid in exploring challenges and opportunities tutors and tutees face when using indigenous languages in the multilingual classroom. Wang (2019) argues that translanguaging should be applied as both an analytical and theoretical framework that permits researchers to rethink and illustrate conglomerate approaches in the classroom set-up that enable students to employ their full linguistic repertoires. In this regard, I see Translanguaging as a relevant framework to manage practices of using indigenous languages in the multilingual classroom because one of the basic tenets of the framework is to empower the languages of the marginalised. I sought what Duarte (2018) proposed; translanguaging could be used as a pedagogical framework to acknowledge other languages and minimise the separation of languages to increase the feasibility of content understanding for students.

I am of the view that translanguaging practice is an act of social justice in education that seeks to realise the voices of the subalterns (García & Leiva, 2014). Hurst and Mona (2017) confirm that translanguaging is a pedagogical strategy that fulfils a socially just element of addressing inequities by recognising the marginalised multilingual students in higher education institutions. In addition, García et al. (2017) proffers that translanguaging can construct learning spaces where students counter against linguistic hierarchies.

“Translanguaging serves as a foundation that lends a theoretical strength to a multilingual pedagogical stance that accepts all resourceful semiotic and linguistic inventions of teachers and students” (Wang, 2019, p. 98)—See also Salmani Nodoushan (2021a, 2022) on semiotics. Lin (2019) echoes similar findings that teachers and students mobilised from all their semiotic resources to “co-construct meaning and understanding” (p. 10). Lin et al. (2020) expand the idea of semiotic resources, arguing that ‘translanguaging flow’ has implications on semiotic resources. Translanguaging flow is the continuous shift and moving of language features that amend the fixed linguistic environment of the classroom that is conventionally defined from a monolingual view. Therefore, translanguaging in a monolingual classroom offers the interconnectedness of semiotic resources in relation to context, space, and time (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a). Furthermore, Wang (2019) insists that:

Translanguaging empowers students with a legitimate voice in class. Students deploy its strategies to achieve learning and interactional objectives while opening themselves up to opportunities to acquire intercultural competence. Therefore, classroom translanguaging studies should include both teacher-led and student-led translanguaging practices.

Vogel and García (2017) aptly outlined three canons that undergird translanguaging theory: Firstly, it posits that individuals select and deploy features from a unitary linguistic repertoire in order to communicate. Secondly, it takes up a perspective on bi- and multilingualism that privileges speakers' personal dynamic linguistic and semiotic practices above the named languages of nations and states. Thirdly, it recognises the material effects of socially constructed named language categories and structuralist language ideologies, especially for minoritised speakers.

These three canons sought to confront the conventional models of bi- and multilingualism by advancing the previously marginalised language practices. It is for this reason that this study is located within translanguaging theory to challenge the current monolingual classroom standard by creating translanguaging spaces which do not alienate and discriminate against tutors and tutees' linguistic varieties. Li (2018) expands on the translanguaging space that is constructed for translanguaging practices. Translanguaging space intends to allow language speakers to disrupt the "ideologically laden dichotomies between the macro and the micro, the societal and the individual and the social and the psychological through interaction" (Li, 2018, p. 23). In addition, translanguaging space consists of a transformative power since it is ever-evolving and creates identities, values and practices. It also couches multilingual 'creativity' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018a) and its capability to disrupt borders between named languages and language hierarchies by altering the behaviour and criticality to employ evidence to ask questions, problematise, and articulate ideas (Li & Zhu, 2013). Translanguaging as a framework for this study sought to ascertain that its applicability emancipates tutors and tutees. This framework "positions bilingual and multilingual practices as the norm" (Kleyn & García, 2019, p. 72).

3. Method

3.1. Ethical clearance

Prior to embarking on the data generation, I applied for permission to conduct this study, and it was granted by the ethics office (GENERAL/HUMAN RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE (GHREC) (Ethical Clearance number: UFS HSD2020/0046/2505).

3.2. Participants

My position at this university, working with tutors and tutees, meant that purposive and convenience sampling would suit this study. The selection of the participants was based on the characteristics in terms of experience, year of tutoring, year of study, and availability. The number of participants was eight tutors and sixteen tutees ($N=24$) from four faculties: Faculty of Humanities, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Economic and Management Sciences, and Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Science.

Participants were given consent to read and understand before deciding to participate in the study. The participants were informed that the data would be used for a master's project and possibly published in an academic journal. Participants were informed that confidentiality and anonymity would be held in the study, which was guaranteed.

To adhere to the standards of research ethics, code system was used to designate the participants; all female respondents' codes start with 'A', whereas all male respondents' codes start with 'B'. In this case: Female respondents will have the codes: AA, AB, AC, AD, AE. Male respondents will have the codes: BA, BB, BC, BD. This was done to anonymise the respondents.

3.3. Procedure

This study follows a case study design that is informed by the context in which the study was undertaken to explore multilingual practices at a South African university. This study explored the use of indigenous languages and English to facilitate multilingual undergraduate tutorials at a South African university. To achieve the aim of this study, I adopted a qualitative research approach. As described by Cresswell (2012), the qualitative research approach is a social inquiry process that aims to explore, interpret and understand the social problem from an array of individual experiences.

To generate data tutors and tutees were invited to participate in the semi-structured interviews, and the tutees for focus group discussions. I would have used observation as an additional tool to generate data. However, due to covid-19 regulations, I employed technological means to schedule interviews and focus group discussions as tutorials were not face-to-face.

Therefore, purposive and convenience sampling qualified to be utilised based on the latter reasons. During the interviews and focus group discussions, the participants were allowed to use the language they were comfortable with. This cohort of participants were speakers of isiZulu, Sesotho, or isiXhosa. The role of translanguaging as a theoretical framework was relevant since the study is focused on the use of language in the multilingual tutorial classroom. During the interviews, the participants tapped into their linguistic repertoires

to articulate their worldviews and realities in the tutorials. The study focused on Sesotho, isiZulu, Afrikaans and English due to the language policy prescripts of the university.

The analysis of empirical data generated from the participants was achieved through the phases of thematic analysis. It started with familiarisation with data followed by coding the data and then collating participants' codes and extracts; searching for themes in this phase, a researcher searches for meaningful and relevant data relating to the research question. The next phase was to review the themes identified in the data to write a detailed analysis for each theme. The last phase was writing up, which is an essential part of the analysis process in thematic analysis (Clarke & Braun, 2013).

4. Findings

Several themes that are discussed below emerged from the data. They include (a) creating a comfortable space for learning and respecting the identity, (b) decolonising tutoring and embracing diverse pedagogies, (c) enhancing content understanding, and (d) encouraging collaborative learning. Two challenges were also identified: (a) lack of language policy knowledge or awareness, and (b) inadequate training on facilitating multilingual tutorials.

The creation of a comfortable space in teaching and learning is vital. In this theme, I provide perceptions of, and discussion on, the use of indigenous languages in a multilingual tutorial classroom.

For me, sir as a tutor, I do facilitate my tutorials using indigenous languages, this is because during tutorials I find it difficult to keep students focused, and one of the strategies to make them feel comfortable is using their own languages during discussion. I also think that indigenous languages carry their identity; this means that if I prevent them from using indigenous languages, I am disadvantaging them. (AA)

However, another tutor provides a differing view.

At first, I used to only strictly use English in the tutorials, but that changed after seeing tutees feeling anxious during tutorials, and when I asked some of them why they were not interacting during the session, they said that they don't know how to express themselves in English. I was very disappointed after getting that feedback after the session. However, I did not stick to English only; I encourage them to use both languages simply because I wanted them to also learn the language, remember the tests, assignments, and examinations are set in English. (AB)

The above excerpts give an account of the occurrences in the tutorials. The recount from one of the tutors indicates that they use indigenous languages to facilitate and create a comfortable tutorial space. In addition, this practice averts from disruption of tutees' identity as the tutor puts it "indigenous languages carry their identity." This is a commendable practice that demonstrates that the tutor is conscious of the linguistic identity of the tutees. It is an authentic argument raised in this regard, as language and identity coexist (Garcia Laborda & Salmani Nodoushan, 2014). Makalela's (2015) findings show that there was a reconfiguration of teacher identity, in a sense that there was a shift from "monolingual teacher to multilingual teacher" (p. 212). He argued that this was sparked by creating multilingual spaces in class. Therefore, I share the same sentiments that language carries identity. Disregarding indigenous languages perform exclusionary linguistic diversity. In a differing conception, a junior tutor argues that she prefers to use both English and indigenous languages. The rationale for this practice is based on the feedback received from tutees on the need for more interaction during group discussions and assessments that are in English. Therefore, she felt that when using both English and indigenous languages, tutees stand a chance of learning and knowing both languages. Findings reported elsewhere also unveil similar trends from the perceptions of the tutors or teachers who permit students to use their indigenous languages.

In the second theme, decolonising tutoring and embracing diverse pedagogies, tutors and tutees were considerate of the contemporary discourses on the decolonisation of the curriculum. In this regard, a multilingual practice, particularly in using translanguaging during their tutorial sessions, assists in decolonising even tutoring pedagogies. The below excerpts provide more details on both accounts of the tutors and tutees.

Sir, I believe in the use of translanguaging during tutorials sessions, as you would be aware that as students we were protesting against western domination. As a tutor, I do not have a right to discriminate in any form, and choosing which language to use in the tutorials is practicing exactly that. My input is that using our languages will help to even decolonise how we do our tutoring. (BA)

Our tutor creates that platform to discuss difficult concepts using translanguaging that for me is a classical way of decolonising education. I agree, sir, that I may be out of line, but our languages could play an important role in decolonising curriculum, learning in our languages helps us to even pass difficult modules, Sir. (AC)

The tutors' views on the decolonisation issue rest on the contemporary discourses on curriculum that is wholly Eurocentric. This tutor believes that

translanguaging as a practice could assist in the current debate on decolonisation even though the comment falls short of how to use these languages to decolonise the curriculum. However, this does not dissuade a point made by these tutors as it resonates with Wa Thiongo's (1986) view that decolonisation's initial practice is in language.

Of interest is the context of whether the current tutoring practices are vested in colonial practices that demand agency and the conventional age of reason to reimagine tutoring practices in higher education. The current tutoring system is part of an extended colonial structure embedded in the curriculum. By this, I imply that decolonising the curriculum would directly affect the modelling of the tutoring system. Further, the ideology of tutoring practices could be found in the colonial form of teaching, where knowledge is centred on tutors, not tutees. The use of indigenous languages in the context of teaching and learning in universities remains monolingual in its form (Makalela, 2021). Thus, this aligns with the notion of the coloniality of language, which continues with the colonial narrative of seeing the languages of the colonised as inferior (Veronelli, 2015). This view is dehumanising in its form and structure.

It is evident that students and teachers draw from their semiotic resources (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a) to construct meaning and understanding (Lin, 2019), so the tutoring system as an extended space of teaching and learning could be seen as continuing with the dehumanisation process as the classroom remains monolingual in a complex multilingual classroom. Therefore, I suggest that tutoring cannot be pushed to the borders or outside of the curriculum; instead, it is located within the curriculum as a form of academic student support. Therefore, Chaka (2020, p. 33) argued that "translanguaging as a disruptive decolonial practice" rejects the notion of colonial and Western-centric perception of languages as bounded, named, and separate units. The question that requires much attention is whether tutoring can be decolonised to a space which embraces linguistic diversity and social justice which rejects the colonial conception of tutorials. This finding is important as limited studies have explored decolonisation from a tutoring point of view.

Under the third theme, enhancing content understanding, tutors and tutees were sharing their experiences on the benefits of using indigenous languages when facilitating multilingual tutorials. The below excerpts are from tutors and tutees who participated in the study.

Using translanguaging could have benefits as students are able to understand what we are discussing during our Geography tutorials. (AD)

In addition, another tutor put forward:

I have seen students engaging much better with the difficult concepts, if I allow them to use their indigenous languages. (BB)

Many studies on translanguaging have shown similar findings; it aids students in understanding complex concepts (Cele, 2021; Hungwe, 2019). In this study, I found that tutors also claim that translanguaging has benefited students in understanding content during their tutorials. This finding corroborates Makalela's (2015) study, which indicated that translanguaging strategy enforces a deeper understanding of the content. Nevertheless, the level of engagement with the problematic concepts increased, especially when they were using their indigenous languages to help them cope with the subject matter. Madiba's (2018) findings also show that the students' learning was maximised during the tutorials when students were using their linguistic repertoires in dealing with the problematic concept.

Tutorials are based on strategies such as collaborative learning—i.e., the fourth theme arguing that translanguaging encourages collaborative learning. Therefore, tutors are encouraged to facilitate their sessions using different approaches to advance collaborative learning as it has been widely reported to have benefited students in myriad ways. Similarly, tutors and tutees reflected on the benefits experienced during their tutorials.

My tutees were able to learn together and share their learning materials during the tutorials; when using translanguaging, it forces them to rely and trust each other's judgement. (BC)

As a student who attended tutorials regularly, I realised that it is easy to work together and collaborate on assessment projects because we can speak different languages during tutorials. Example, sir, is when we were discussing 'state' as a concept during group discussions; we used our languages, but we presented in English so that everyone could understand our presentation. (AE)

From the above excerpts, it is clear that translanguaging fosters collaborative learning amongst tutees, as reported by a tutor. It also moves beyond collaborative learning as it helps tutees to use it as a strategy to build rapport amongst themselves. Another finding also confirms that translanguaging as a pedagogical practice has existed in the tutorials. This can be observed from AE's excerpt that they had their group discussion using their home languages (input) and presented in English (output). Leach (2015), reporting on a multilingual tutorial indicated that many students posited that their home language helped them engage in the discussions during tutorials. This indicates that tutorials are safe spaces that can be used to promote diverse languages

brought by students. Cele (2021) opines that African languages could be utilised to aid students in comprehending subject concepts. This argument is imperative for the success of facilitating multilingual tutorials and to achieve the goal of the peer tutorials, which is to help students engage and collaborate with the content with their peers. This view aligns with Li's (2018) on translanguaging space, allowing language speakers to interact and articulate their views using their creativity.

Two challenges also emerged from the data: (a) lack of language policy knowledge or awareness, and (b) inadequate training on facilitating multilingual tutorials. It should be noted that language awareness is pivotal in higher education. The institutional language policies always follow a stakeholder engagement process during the language policy formulation.

To be honest with you, sir, it is for first the time I hear that there is a language policy at our university. I wonder if it is me only who does not know about it because even in our student caucuses I have never heard anyone talking about. Then my question would be how would it be implemented if we do not know anything about it? I am not being negative towards it, but I need clarity from the people who came up with it. (AF)

Nkile ka utlwa ho bua ka yona in passing fela tsebo ka yona hakena yona. Fela ke nahana leano la ho qala ka ditutorials le nepahetse. Then haretsebe ka language policy, mohlomong rehloka ho tsebiswa ka yona. In translation [Trans: I once heard being talked about it in passing, but I don't have any knowledge about it. But, I think the plan to start with tutorials is correct. Then we don't know about language policy, maybe we need to be informed about it.] (BD)

Knowledge about language policy seems to be eluding both tutors and tutees. It can be inferred from some inputs that language policy must be published for the student population to know about it. As one can learn from BD that it is for the first time that she hears something about language policy, this is concerning because these are the people who are supposed to be informed about the processes undertaken in the development of the language policy.

As a tutor, I have not been trained on how to facilitate students who speak different languages, and we know that our campus is diverse. So, we need intensive training in order to ensure that we don't mislead tutees. (BE)

Sometimes it is even difficult to engage with our fellow tutees with whom we attend tutorials together because our tutor cannot manage tutorials

properly and end up being unfair to the speakers of other languages. I feel like our tutors are not well equipped, they will need to be equipped with strategies on how to manage a diverse classroom. (AG)

In the latter excerpts, it is clear from tutors' and tutees' perspectives that it is essential to be trained on how to facilitate multilingual tutorials and manage a diverse classroom. This points to a second challenge, i.e., inadequate training on facilitating multilingual tutorials. As BE put it, they need intensive training not to mislead their tutees. This finding is crucial as tutors are encouraged to avoid leading their tutees astray as such a practice will devalue the need for tutorials. Consequently, tutor practices are observed by their tutees; this can be noted from AG commentary that his tutor could not manage a diverse classroom and further submits that tutors need to be equipped on how to manage the diverse classroom to avert bad practices. The question, therefore, will be: How do you train tutors to facilitate multilingual tutorials?

5. Conclusion

As possible solutions to the identified challenges, three suggestions are made: (a) provision of language policy awareness, (b) tutor training on facilitating multilingual tutorials, and (c) decolonising tutoring classroom practices.

The two excerpts below are essential to consider as these tutors appear to agree with each other on the provision of the workshop on language policy.

As tutors, we need to be provided with the workshop so that we know about the university language policy. (AA)

I do not know language policy of the university. I have never seen it. I guess it will be helpful to be provided with workshop or training for us understand how language policy is formulated. (AB)

It is, therefore, cumbersome to note that tutors, which assume the status of being senior students, are not knowledgeable about the language policy of the university. This is despite the policy being public on the university website. For example, submission from one of the participants believes that as tutors, they need to be provided with the workshop so that we know about the university language policy.

According to tutors, this evidence is crucial in successfully implementing the multilingual language policy. In support of this claim, one of the tutors proclaimed that they do not know the university's language policy. The stance from the tutor is eminent that tutors need to be provided with a session where language policy will be discussed in detail, including the planning and the goal of the university regarding its implementation strategy in the multilingual

tutorials and university at large. Therefore, language policy awareness is vital in managing multilingual classrooms. Another point to note is that one of the tutors believed that translanguaging will assist them in aligning their tutorial practices with the language policy plans. Therefore, the provision of workshops, according to this tutor, will aid in a more significant deal to align implementation plans with translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy.

Tutors have shown that it is paramount to be fully equipped with skills and strategies for facilitating multilingual tutorials. Moreover, it can be argued that tutor training is a barometer for a quality tutor programme. This can be achieved in different ways to find a suitable strategy that befits the context of the students and tutors. Furthermore, when compiling the training materials, it is essential that training is tutor-centred in that it maintains the student learning to the core, encouraging tutors to know and understand students' linguistic profiles before resuming their tutorials, even though these findings contradict what Thonus (2014) suggested: tutors need one-size-fits-all training.

The context of this study is different from the suggestion of Thonus, though. This makes it a necessity to design tutor training that is specific to the needs of the tutors and tutees. This approach will aid them when crafting their tutor session plan, for them to be conscious of their students and their diverse languages. In their session plans, tutors need to analyse approaches or strategies they plan to deploy during the tutorial: to design a lesson plan with a mindset of multilingual students-core. The process could be cyclical because tutors reflect on whether they have achieved their plans after their session. By so doing, they will be engaged in a self-reflexive process (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2011) that assumes the necessity to know their context and the type of tutees who attend tutorials. Notably, there are scant studies that focus on tutor training for facilitating multilingual classrooms. Therefore, these findings contribute to a meager body of literature on tutor training, particularly facilitating multilingual classrooms.

The need to decolonise tutoring classrooms cannot be ignored. As we have seen from the findings, the tutoring system as an extended teaching and learning space appears to carry over monolingual practices. In nature, the monolingual practices are dehumanising to students for who English is not their native language. Worth to note is the proposal to decolonise multilingualism (Ndhlovu and Makalela, 2021). This proposal is essential considering the nature of the classroom practices marginalising other students. It is evident that tutors and tutees mobilise from their semiotic resources to collaborate, meaning-making and understanding (Lin, 2019). So, there is an urgent need to decolonise the tutoring system to one that will appreciate linguistic fluidity. A decolonised tutoring system views multilingual tutors and tutees as complete

and not from a deficit view of monolingual bias. It can be seen that the current tutoring system confirms “monolanguaging” practices of dehumanising (Veronelli, 2015).

As a ‘washback’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of this paper, it is essential to note that translanguaging pedagogical practices offers opportunities for multilingual students. However, in a context where the tutoring system is captured in a monolingual practice that dehumanises tutors and tutees, translanguaging will not be effective. Translanguaging has shown that it helps tutors and tutees to deploy their semiotic resources to create meaning, collaborate, and create a comfortable space for learning. In spaces such as tutorials, the coloniality of language exists. There is an urgent need to attend to linguistic and epistemic challenges that are created through this system. The tutoring system is vital for students to engage and collaborate with their peers in a classroom that respects their linguistic repertoires. In that regard, tutorial systems need to be critically seen within the core of the curriculum, not in the periphery, as it has the potential to silence the voices of the tutor and tutee. This will aid in contributing to the decolonisation of the curriculum through the use of indigenous languages and embracing linguistic diversity in the tutorials. It can be deduced that it is essential that tutors are trained on how to facilitate multilingual tutorials using translanguaging. Training is essential for ensuring tutors understand and are exposed to multilingual classroom realities so that, when facilitating their tutorials, they create a safe space for both a tutor and tutee. Therefore, I can conclude that translanguaging as a pedagogical practice offers new opportunities to explore other pedagogical ‘affordances’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), in a tutorial system.

Notes:

1. Many scholars have done extensive research on translanguaging and other relevant topics including activism, diversity, decolonisation epistemologies, multilingualism, translanguaging, equity, social justice, and other relevant (socio)educational topics; please see recent works by Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marias (2024), Mapuya (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Xu and Fang (2024)—among others.

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